

AZERBAIJAN REPUBLIC
BAKU CITY EXECUTIVE AUTHORITY
DEPARTMENT OF HOUSING AND COMMUNAL SERVICES

No. 3-52-13/2-387/2024

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To the Director of the Institute of Philosophy and Sociology National Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan Mr. Ilham Mammadzade

In response to your letter dated 19.02.2024, Ref. No. 8-1-10/2-35/2024

Dear Ilham Muallim,

We inform you that the Department of Housing and Communal Services of the Baku City Executive Authority has reviewed the monograph by the leading researcher of the Institute of Philosophy and Sociology of the National Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan, Doctor of Philosophical Sciences Aydin Alizade, titled *Communal Services in Azerbaijan in the Mid-20th Century: A Historical-Sociological Study*.

The presented historical-sociological monograph is dedicated to a previously unexplored topic and is of particular interest and practical significance for local (district and city) executive authorities of the Azerbaijan Republic. During the period under study, the country's communal services were managed by executive committees. Currently, relevant economic institutions continue to operate in these service sectors, and in the capital, the management of housing, communal, and sanitation services is carried out by the Department of Housing and Communal Services of the Baku City Executive Authority and its structural subdivisions.

The study is based on archival materials, which enhances the significance of this work and ensures its novelty. The monograph contains highly valuable new information and statistical data that can be used in further research based on the tables compiled by the author.

The development of communal services is built upon the foundation of the Soviet era. It is impossible to achieve objective scientific results without studying the achievements and shortcomings of the period covered by the monograph and comparing them with modern developments. It should be noted that, currently, many reconstruction projects in the communal sector are carried out based on designs developed during the Soviet period, making the examination of the communal infrastructure of that time relevant for ensuring a high level of service in accordance with modern requirements. The study provides an opportunity to address negative processes from the past that are incompatible with contemporary standards.

It should be highlighted that the monograph, dedicated to the history of communal services in Azerbaijan in the mid-20th century, is significant for institutions operating in this field for the following reasons:

Firstly, it presents evolutionary processes. Studying history helps understand how the structures of communal services in Azerbaijan were formed and developed in the past. This enables opportunities for forecasting future challenges and developing more effective strategies.

Secondly, it facilitates resource optimization. The analysis of historical data allows for the identification of successful practices and mistakes that can be used to optimize current processes. This contributes to resource conservation and improved service quality.

Thirdly, it provides an understanding of the importance of legal aspects. The monograph examines legislative changes and reforms related to the activities of the communal sector. These aspects can assist executive authorities in adapting to modern requirements and standards.

Fourthly, it emphasizes the importance of education and knowledge exchange in the economic sphere. The monograph can serve as educational material for specialists and employees working in the communal services sector. Additionally, this work can facilitate the exchange of experiences among communal services in various cities and regions.

Thus, the monograph dedicated to the history of communal services can contribute to informed decision-making, improving the level and quality of citizens' lives, and holds practical significance.

Sincerely,

Chairman

Rafail Mekhraliyev

(Signature)

(Translation from Azerbaijani)